

THE IMPACT OF BINARY ENCODING TECHNIQUES ON COMPUTER SYSTEM SERVICING SUBJECT AMONG INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of binary encoding techniques on ICT students' learning in the Computer System Servicing (CSS) subject. The research aims to assess students' comprehension, practical application, and academic performance concerning binary encoding. A quantitative research design was employed, utilizing a survey questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument. The survey was administered to 84 ICT students, and the gathered data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency and percentage distributions. Results indicate that most students find binary encoding beneficial for enhancing problem-solving and analytical skills, with hands-on activities reinforcing theoretical knowledge. A positive correlation was observed between mastery of binary encoding and improved academic performance.

Keywords: *Binary Encoding Techniques, ICT students, Computer System Servicing (CSS), Problem-solving skills, Analytical skills*

INTRODUCTION

Binary is necessary for us as humans to operate, build, and program in our lives now because binary is what the cutting edge of all modern computing has arrowed itself

toward. Binary is a choice of systems which computers use internally for tasks such as storing, processing, and transmitting large amounts of data to support the operation of sophisticated applications and OS. In addition to that, Binary allows for stable digital communication over the internet as well as telecommunication while making sure information can be transmitted securely and efficiently. More importantly, support ranges from everyday devices to secure online transactions.

Students use different devices everyday such as smartphones, laptops, and computers. For instance, students use computers for school projects, gaming, access to the internet, and entertainment. From laptop to gaming or consoles, all the devices used Binary to store and process data. The importance of binary encoding is the use of 0s and 1s. It represents the data, it is a fundamental concept in computer science. The importance lies in its ability to translate the complex information into a language that computers can understand and to process it efficiently. In fact the smallest unit of Binary is a bit which can be either 0 or 1. By combining the multiple bits computer devices can represent a vast range of information.

This study looks into how understanding the basics of binary encoding can be applied in real-world tasks related to Computer System Servicing. As Awati (2022) points out, binary code forms the core of how computers operate, using simple 0s and 1s to send instructions to both hardware and software. By exploring this relationship during the senior high school period, this study aims to determine the impact of Binary Encoding Technique on Computer System Servicing subject among Information Communication Technology students.

Research Questions

This study aims to evaluate the impact of Binary Encoding Techniques on the performance of Information Communication Technology (ICT) students in the Computer System Servicing Subject.

1. How may binary encoding be described in terms of:
 - a. Alphanumeric
 - b. Binary Coded Decimal; and
 - c. ASCII encoding
 2. How can the ICT students' performance in Computer System Servicing subject be described in terms of:
 - a. Problem-solving and Analytical skills
 - b. How will the students apply concepts during laboratory activities; and
 - c. Academic grades
 3. Is there a significant relationship between Binary Encoding Techniques and the performance of ICT students in the Computer System Servicing subject?
 4. Based on the findings of the study, what actions can be derived to enhance the learning and application of Binary Encoding Techniques in ICT education?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Method

This study used a descriptive method to describe the impact of Binary Encoding Techniques on ICT Students' performance on Computer System Servicing Subject. A convenience sampling technique was applied, where ICT students from Headwaters College with experience and available in Computer System Servicing (CSS) were selected. By using convenience sampling, the study reflects the perspectives of students who were readily available during data gathering, though it may not fully represent all ICT students' experiences with the topic.

Research Locale

This study will be conducted at Headwaters College-Elizabeth Campus school, located at the Road 1 Minuyan 2 of San Jose Del Monte. It is a private secondary school that caters to Grade 11 to 12 students. HCI is called a source of quality and total (intellectual, physical, emotional and social) learning, but of Christian development as well. The school has six strands, and the population of campus is 2266.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study are Senior High School students in Headwaters College-Elizabeth Campus Grade 12 Information and Communication Technology Students School Year 2024-2025. A total of 80 students will be selected through purposive sampling to participate in the study.

Population and Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling was used in this study. The respondents selected were 100 from five 5 sections of the grade 12 ICT strand from Headwaters College-Elizabeth Campus. In addition, the ICT strand is more proficient in using computers and knowledgeable in binary encoding for their proficiency in using computers. The researchers chose convenience sampling for only those who were easy to access and willing to participate were selected to answer surveys and it will also make time and finances easier.

Development and Validation of Data Gathering Instruments

This study will use a survey questionnaire to collect data for the investigation of the impact of binary encoding techniques on the performance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) students in their CSS subject. The research instruments were first validated by professional English teachers from public schools. Data were collected through a survey instrument consisting of Likert scale items through

Google forms. It was designed with three sections to assess students' understanding and application of binary encoding in CSS. This survey questionnaire will be given to Grade 12 ICT students enrolled at Headwaters College-Elizabeth Campus who can answer the survey questionnaire and will be conducted during school class time with a time allocation of 5 minutes per student.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Statistical treatment is when a statistical method is applied to a data set to draw meaning from it. Statistical treatment will be either descriptive statistics, which describes the relationship between variables in a population, or inferential statistics, which tests a hypothesis by making inferences from the collected data. (DiscoverPhDs, 2020).

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The study will be conducted to ICT students but limited to other strands. The research administered to the ICT students of Headwaters College. However, it will only be conducted to Elizabeth Campus. The study will gather the data for the school year 2024 - 2025 but data to be analyze shall cover the First Semester only, Second Semester is not included. The study to be conducted and shall gather data from specialized subject of ICT, whereas other cores and applied subjects are truncated from this study.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the study on the impact of binary encoding techniques on ICT students' learning in the Computer System Servicing (CSS) subject. The data were gathered using a survey questionnaire administered to 84 ICT students, with responses analyzed through descriptive statistics, including frequency and percentage distributions. The findings are organized into three sections: students' comprehension of binary encoding techniques, the impact of these techniques on academic performance, and potential actions to enhance learning and application in ICT education. The results provide insights into students' understanding of binary encoding concepts, their ability to apply these in practical settings, and their academic performance in tasks involving binary encoding.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Grade and Section

Figure 1. Respondents

Section 1: BINARY ENCODING

1. Opinion on how easy Binary Encoding to comprehend

Figure 2. Binary Encoding Techniques and Students' Comprehension

Figure 2 shows that 57 or 67.9 percent of the respondents agreed that Binary Encoding Techniques are easy to comprehend in the context of the CSS Subject. On the other hand, 19 or 22.6 percent disagreed while 12 or 14.3 percent strongly agreed and 6 or 7.1 percent of the respondents strongly disagreed. It is evident that the majority of the respondents find Binary Encoding easy to understand.

2. Rating how Understanding BCD (Binary Coded Decimal) encoding enhances comprehension of numeric data in CSS

Understanding BCD (Binary Coded Decimal) encoding enhances my comprehension of numeric data in CSS.
84 responses

Figure 3. Binary Coded Decimal and Comprehension Enhancement

Figure 3 illustrates that the majority of the respondents, which makes up to 65 or 77.4 percent, agreed that understanding BCD (Binary Coded Decimal) encoding enhances comprehension of numeric data in CSS while 12 or 14.3 percent strongly agreed. In contrast, 10 or 11.9 of the respondents disagreed and 1 or 1.2 percent strongly disagreed.

3. Opinion if making the 7 Segment project in CSS enhance knowledge in BCD (Binary Coded Decimal)

Making the 7 Segment project in CSS enhances my knowledge in BCD (Binary Coded Decimal)
84 responses

Figure 4. 7 Segment and Binary Coded Decimal

It shows that 59 or 70.2 percent of the respondents agreed that making the 7 Segment project in CSS enhances their knowledge in BCD (Binary Coded Decimal) while 16 or 19 percent of them agreed. On the other hand, 13 or 15.5 percent of the respondents disagreed while 1 or 1.2 percent strongly disagreed.

4. Rating how ICT students understand ASCII encoding to represent text in computer systems

I understand how ASCII encoding is used to represent text in computer systems.
84 responses

Figure 5. Understanding of ASCII Encoding

Figure 5 illustrates that the majority of the respondents (48 or 57.1 percent) agreed that they understand how ASCII encoding is used to represent text in computer systems. Additionally, 10 or 11.9 percent strongly agreed. In contrast, 24 or 28.6 percent of the respondents disagreed and 6 or 7.1 percent strongly disagreed.

5. Opinion on how Alphanumeric encoding helps ICT students understand how characters and numbers are represented in computer systems.

Alphanumeric encoding helps me understand how characters and numbers are represented in computer systems.
84 responses

Figure 6. Alphanumeric and Understanding of Characters and Numbers.

This shows that 63 or 75 percent of the respondents agreed that Alphanumeric encoding helps them understand how characters and numbers are represented in

computer system while 11 or 13.1 percent strongly agreed. On the other hand, 12 or 14.3 percent of the respondents disagreed and 3 or 3.6 percent strongly disagree.

Section 2: ICT Students' Performance in Computer System Servicing Subject.

1. Opinion on how learning binary encoding techniques has improved ICT students' problem-solving skills

Learning binary encoding techniques has improved my problem-solving skills.

84 responses

Figure 7. Binary Encoding Techniques and Problem-Solving Skills

According to the survey results among ICT students, (70.2%) of respondents agree that binary encoding techniques has improved their problem-solving skills, while (19.0%) disagree, (14.3%) strongly agree, and (2.4%) strongly disagree.

2. ICT students' capabilities to apply binary encoding concepts effectively during laboratory activities.

I can apply binary encoding concepts effectively during laboratory activities.

84 responses

Figure 8. Binary Encoding and Laboratory Activities.

According to the survey results among ICT students, (67.9%) of respondents agree that binary encoding is effective in laboratory activities, while (23.8%) disagree, (10.7%) strongly agree, and (3.36%) strongly disagree.

3. Rating ICT students' hands-on skills enhancement involving Binary Encoding Techniques.

Figure 9. Laboratory Activities and Hands-On Skills

69.0% of respondents agreed that laboratory activities involving Binary Encoding Techniques enhanced their hands-on skills. while 17.9% Disagreed, 14.3% Strongly Agreed and 4.8% Strongly Disagreed.

4. Opinion on how understanding Binary Encoding techniques has a positive impact on CSS grades.

Figure 10. Binary Encoding Techniques and Grades in CSS subject

65.5% of respondents agreed that my understanding of Binary Encoding Techniques has positive impact on my CSS grades. while 20.2% Strongly Agreed, 16.7% Disagreed and 6.0% Strongly Disagreed.

5. Opinion on how mastery of binary encoding techniques helps ICT students' perform well in written and practical assessments in CSS.

Mastery of binary encoding techniques helps me perform well in written and practical assessments in CSS.

84 responses

Figure 11. Binary Encoding Techniques and Written and Practical Assessments in CSS subject

71.4% of the respondents agreed that Binary Encoding Techniques can helps to perform well in written and practical assessment in CSS. while 10.7% Strongly Agreed, 21.4% Disagreed and 3.6% Strongly Disagreed.

6. Rating ICT students' capabilities to apply binary encoding concepts effectively during laboratory activities.

I can apply binary encoding concepts effectively during laboratory activities.

84 responses

Figure 12. Binary Encoding Application in Laboratory Activities

60.7% of the respondents agreed that Binary Encoding can apply effectively during laboratory activities. While 10.7% Strongly Agreed, 27.4% Disagreed and 8.3 Strongly of the respondents Disagreed.

7. Opinion on how Binary Encoding Techniques have enhanced ICT students' analytical and critical thinking skills in the CSS subject.

Binary Encoding Techniques have enhanced my analytical and critical thinking skills in the CSS subject.

84 responses

Figure 13. Binary Encoding Techniques and Analytical and Critical Thinking Skills

Based on the survey, 71.4% of respondents agreed that binary encoding techniques have enhanced their analytical and critical thinking skills in the CSS subject, while 13.1% strongly agreed, 15.5% disagreed, and 7.1% strongly disagreed.

8. Rating how the application of BCD (Binary Coded Decimal) in the 7 Segment project has improved ICT students' problem-solving skills.

The application of BCD (Binary Coded Decimal) in our 7 Segment project has improved my problem-solving skills.

84 responses

Figure 14. BCD and Problem-Solving Skills

65.5% of the respondents agreed that using BCD (Binary Coded Decimal) in their 7-segments project helped them solve problems better, while 17.9% strongly agreed, 17.9% disagreed, and 4.8% strongly disagreed.

9. Opinion on how consistent ICT students' achieve good grades in tasks and projects involving binary encoding techniques.

I consistently achieve good grades in tasks and projects involving binary encoding techniques.
84 responses

Figure 15. Binary Encoding Techniques and Grades.

63.1% of students agreed that they consistently Achieve good grades in projects involving Binary Encoding Techniques while 21.4% of the students disagreed, 21.4% of the students strongly agreed and 4.8% strongly disagreed.

Section 3: Actions that can be derived to enhance the learning and application of Binary Encoding Techniques in ICT Education.

1. Opinion on how hands-on activities involving real-world applications of binary encoding techniques should be increased in CSS classes.

Hands-on activities involving real-world applications of binary encoding techniques should be increased in CSS classes.
84 responses

Figure 16. Hands-on Activities in CSS classes

70.2% of the students agreed that real world application of Binary Encoding Techniques should be increased in CSS classes while 14.3% of the students disagreed, 19% strongly agreed and 1.1% of the students strongly disagreed.

2. Opinion on how additional practical exercises on binary encoding techniques would enhance ICT students’ learning experience.

I believe additional practical exercises on binary encoding techniques would enhance my learning experience.
84 responses

Figure 17. Additional Practical Exercises Enhancing Learning Experience

78.6% of 84 respondents agreed that I believe additional practical exercise on binary encoding techniques would enhance my learning experience. while 10.7% Strongly Agree, 13.1% Disagree and 2.4% Strongly Disagree.

3. Opinion on how additional resources, such as video tutorials, and practice modules would help ICT students’ learn binary encoding techniques more effectively.

Additional resources, such as video tutorials and practice modules, would help me learn binary encoding techniques more effectively.
84 responses

Figure 18. Additional Resources and Learning Binary Encoding Techniques

65.5% of 84 respondents agreed that Additional resources, such as video tutorials and practice modules, would help me learn binary encoding techniques more effectively. while 19.0% Strongly Agree, 17.9% Disagree and 4.8% Strongly Disagree.

4. Opinion on how the curriculum should include more advanced and practical applications of binary encoding techniques.

The curriculum should include more advanced and practical applications of binary encoding techniques.

84 responses

Figure 19. Binary Encoding Techniques and Curriculum

It shows that 54 or 64.3 percent of the respondents agreed that the curriculum should include more advanced and practical applications of binary encoding techniques while 15 or 17.9 percent agreed. In contrary, 16 or 19 percent of the respondents disagreed and 5 or 6 percent strongly disagreed.

5. Opinion on regular quizzes and evaluations on binary encoding techniques would help ICT students' track my learning progress.

Regular quizzes and evaluations on binary encoding techniques would help me track my learning progress.

84 responses

Figure 20. Regular Quizzes and Learning Progress

Figure 20 illustrates that the majority of respondents (59 or 70.2%) agreed that Regular quizzes and evaluations on binary encoding techniques would help me track their learning progress. Additionally, 14 respondents (16.7%) strongly agreed. In contrast, 11 respondents (13.1%) disagreed, while 6 respondents (7.1%) strongly disagreed.

DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the analysis of data from the previous chapter or the results which were gathered through survey questionnaires. The data focuses on students' comprehension of Binary Encoding Techniques, their performance and their application in Computer System Servicing (CSS). The results were analyzed using descriptive statistics in terms of percentages and trends. This analysis helps us examine whether Binary Encoding Techniques truly make a difference in how students did learn CSS. Each figure will be explained in detail to highlight important insights and what they mean for students' learning experiences.

Analysis of Data

I. Binary Encoding

a. Binary Encoding Techniques and Students' Comprehension

The majority of respondents find binary encoding techniques accessible and understandable within the context of CSS. This suggests that binary encoding is not a major obstacle for students learning the subject, and it is a topic that most students are comfortable with.

The results indicate that the majority of respondents find binary encoding techniques easy to comprehend within the context of the CSS subject.

b. Binary Coded Decimal and Comprehension Enhancement

The results shows that the majority of students recognize the importance of BCD in enhancing their knowledge of numeric data in CSS. With 77.4% agreeing and 14.3% strongly agreeing, it shows that learning BCD encoding positively contributes to their comprehension. However, a small percentage (11.9%) disagreed, implying that some students may require alternative learning strategies or additional support to fully grasp the concept.

c. 7-Segment and Binary Coded Decimal

The majority of respondents find the 7 Segment project helpful for reinforcing their knowledge of BCD. The positive response implies that hands-on projects like this one can effectively reinforce theoretical learning by providing practical applications of the concept.

Yunman Hao's 2020 article, BCD to 7-Segment Decoder, looks more closely at how this process works in digital systems and how it affects the way we interact with technology. It really shows how essential binary encoding is in helping us understand and use tech in everyday life. The results indicate that a majority of respondents feel that the 7 Segment project in CSS enhances their knowledge of BCD.

d. Understanding of ASCII Encoding

While most respondents understand ASCII encoding, (28.6%) disagreed or strongly disagreed. This could suggest that there are challenges or gaps still in understanding how ASCII encoding works. And improved ICT curriculum is recommended. The results suggest that while most respondents understand ASCII encoding, a significant portion of them still struggles with this concept.

e. Alphanumeric and Understanding of Characters and Numbers.

The majority of respondents find alphanumeric encoding helpful in understanding the representation of characters and numbers. This shows that students appreciate how alphanumeric encoding simplifies the process of representing data in computer systems and aids their learning. The results show that most respondents agree that alphanumeric encoding helps them understand character and number representation in computer systems.

II. ICT Students' Performance in Computer System Servicing Subject.

a. Binary Encoding Techniques and Problem-Solving Skills

This shows that majority of the respondents (70.2%) believe that learning binary encoding techniques has improved their problem-solving skills suggesting that the techniques contribute to enhancing students' critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

The result indicates that learning binary encoding techniques improved the problem-solving skills of ICT Students. There's an idea of Developing Logical-Mathematical Intelligence, which explains how systems like binary encoding improve our ability to reason and solve problems (Vinney, 2024). These skills are crucial not only in technology but also in decision-making and innovation, as noted in Critical Thinking and Problem Solving (Stefanic, n.d.).

b. Binary Encoding and Laboratory Activities

It shows that a majority of respondents (67.9%) agree that they can apply binary encoding concepts effectively during laboratory activities, indicating that students are able to transfer theoretical knowledge into practical applications during hands-on tasks.

Hence, the result indicates that knowledge about Binary Encoding Concepts could be used effectively during laboratory activities.

c. Laboratory Activities and Hands-On Skills

Most respondents (69.0%) agree that laboratory activities involving binary encoding techniques enhance their hands-on skills, highlighting the value of practical experience in reinforcing theoretical learning. Therefore, this shows that laboratory activities with Binary Encoding Techniques can enhance hands-on skills.

d. Binary Encoding Techniques and Grades in CSS subject

65.5% of respondents believe their understanding of binary encoding techniques has positively influenced their grades in CSS, suggesting that mastery of these concepts plays a significant role in performance in their specialization subject. The result indicates that ICT students' grades have increased by understanding Binary Encoding.

e. Binary Encoding Techniques and Written and Practical Assessments in CSS subject

This shows that a high percentage of respondents (71.4%) agree that mastery of binary encoding techniques helps them perform well in both written and practical assessments, emphasizing the direct link between understanding binary encoding and success in assessments. Therefore, Binary Encoding positively affects ICT Students' written and practical assessments.

f. Binary Encoding Application in Laboratory Activities

This reveals that while 60.7% of respondents agree that they can effectively apply binary encoding concepts in laboratory activities, (27.4%) disagrees, indicating some students may need additional support to fully understand the applications of these concepts. Hence, majority of the students actually apply Binary Encoding concepts effectively in laboratory activities.

g. Binary Encoding Techniques and Analytical and Critical Thinking Skills

71.4% of respondents agrees that binary encoding techniques have enhanced their analytical and critical thinking skills, suggesting that these techniques contribute to the development of higher-order thinking in the CSS subject. The result indicates that respondents' analytical and critical thinking skills have been enhanced with the knowledge of Binary Encoding Techniques.

h. BCD and Problem-Solving Skills

This suggests that 65.5% of respondents agree that the use of BCD in the 7 Segment project has improved their problem-solving skills, showing the effectiveness of this hands-on project in strengthening students' ability to solve complicated problems. Hence, the results indicates that the 7-segment project involving BCD has a significant impact on their problem-solving skills. A study by Planton et al. (2021) found that knowing how binary sequences work, particularly BCD can help improve memory and make problem-solving easier by allowing people to think in a more organized way.

i. Binary Encoding Techniques and Grades

This shows that 63.1% of respondents agree that they consistently achieve good grades in tasks and projects involving binary encoding techniques, indicating that students who understand binary encoding techniques tend to perform well academically in related tasks.

Binary encoding, which organizes information using just 1s and 0s, can really help students understand and remember things better. A study by Shani et al. (2023) found that students who used this method in a tech class scored better on tests, showing that it helps with learning. The research also suggests that binary encoding might help improve students' critical thinking and how they process visual information, making it a useful tool in tech education. Additionally, a review by Montuori et al. (2024) found that learning coding greatly boosts problem-solving skills, with the biggest impact on this area.

III. Actions that can be derived to enhance the learning and application of Binary Encoding Techniques in ICT Education

a. Hands-on Activities in CSS classes.

Majority of students (70.2%) believe hands-on activities involving real-world applications of binary encoding techniques should be increased in CSS suggesting that students value practical, real-world applications to enhance their understanding of the CSS subject. Hence, the results indicate that Binary Encoding should be improved more to the ICT curriculum leading to more enhanced knowledge of the students.

b. Additional Practical Exercises Enhancing Learning Experiences

The results show that a large proportion of respondents (78.6%) believe that additional practical exercises would enhance their learning experience, emphasizing the importance of more hands-on practice to solidify their understanding of binary encoding techniques.

c. Additional Resources and Learning Binary Encoding Techniques.

The results suggest that 65.5% of respondents agree that additional resources like video tutorials and practice modules would help them learn binary encoding techniques more effectively, indicating a desire for supplementary materials to support their learning.

A study on ICT in the Philippines found that while many schools have started using digital tools, the lack of proper training and resources prevents them from making the most of it (Tomaro, 2018). This shows that without the right support, students may struggle to develop the technical skills they need. Another study showed that even when digital tools are available in classrooms, they are not always used well, which affects how students learn skills like encoding (Kilaton, et. al 2024). In universities, research from the Polytechnic University of the Philippines found that students still have a hard time understanding technical topics because of weak ICT training and poor facilities (Castolo, 2004). These studies show that schools need to improve how they use technology so students can better learn Binary Encoding.

d. Binary Encoding Techniques and Curriculum

The results show that 64.3% of respondents agree that the curriculum should include more advanced and practical applications of binary encoding techniques, suggesting that students feel the need for deeper and more complex topics to be covered in their education.

e. Regular Quizzes and Learning Progress

The results indicate that a significant number of respondents (70.2%) agree that regular quizzes and evaluations would help them track their learning progress, emphasizing the importance of assessments in monitoring and reinforcing their understanding of binary encoding techniques.

Conclusions

This study shows that Binary Encoding Techniques play an important role in how ICT students learn in their Computer System Servicing (CSS) subject. Most students (67.9%) said Binary Encoding is easy to understand, but some (22.6%) still struggle with it. Among the different techniques, BCD encoding helped 77.4% of students understand numeric data better, while ASCII encoding (57.1%) made it easier for them to grasp how text is represented in computers.

When it comes to student performance, the results show that learning Binary Encoding helped improve problem-solving skills for 70.2% of students. Hands-on activities, like lab exercises and projects, also helped, with 69.0% agreeing that these activities made them better at applying what they learned. In addition, 65.5% of students

believed that knowing Binary Encoding had a positive effect on their CSS grades, while 71.4% said it sharpened their analytical and critical thinking skills.

The study also found that students want more practical learning experiences to improve their understanding of Binary Encoding. 70.2% think that real-world applications should be included more in CSS classes, and 78.6% believe that extra exercises would help them learn better. Many students also feel that video tutorials and practice modules (65.5%) and regular quizzes (70.2%) would be useful in tracking their learning progress.

With these findings, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis (H_a) as a result, the study claims that Binary Encoding Techniques have significant impact on ICT students' performance in their CSS subject. To help students learn better, teachers can improve their teaching methods by adding more hands-on activities, practice exercises, and additional learning materials.

Recommendations

1. Increase hands-on activities in CSS classes to enhance students' understanding of Binary Encoding.

Instead of only discussing Binary Encoding in theory, students should engage in practical exercises such as coding tasks, circuit simulations, or using software that demonstrates how binary data works. This approach will help them understand concepts more effectively.

2. Incorporate more real-world applications of Binary Encoding to improve problem-solving skills.

Teaching students how Binary Encoding is used in areas like data storage, networking, and cybersecurity will help them see its importance. Applying these concepts to real-life situations will also strengthen their ability to solve problems.

3. Provide additional learning resources like video tutorials and interactive modules

Different students have different learning styles. Offering extra resources like instructional videos, interactive exercises, and step-by-step guides can make complex topics easier to understand and reinforce classroom lessons..

4. Implement regular assessments (quizzes and evaluations) to track students' progress.

Short quizzes, evaluations, and feedback sessions will help identify students' strengths and areas that need improvement. Regular assessments will allow teachers to adjust their lessons accordingly and provide additional support when needed.

5. Enhance the curriculum by including advanced and practical applications of Binary Encoding.

Expanding the lessons to cover more in-depth topics, such as encryption and data compression, will give students a deeper understanding of Binary Encoding. This will also better prepare them for careers in technology and information systems.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers made sure to provide respondents with informed consent. The respondents were free to withdraw from the study any time. The researchers made sure that all personal information of the respondents remained confidential. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided and the results were used solely for research.

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